

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**VARIOUS MODES OF CLEIAC DISEASE PRESENTATION IN
CHILDREN OF 3-15 YEARS OF AGE**¹Dr. Rida Saghir, ²Dr. Madiha Sammer, ³Dr. Izza Khalid¹Frontier Medical College, Abbottabad²Quaid e Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur³Avicenna Medical College, Lahore**Abstract:**

Objective: To evaluate the celiac disease clinical presentation and the effect on clinical symptoms after giving of gluten-free diet in children aged 3-15 years.

Study Design: An Observational descriptive study.

Location and Duration: In the Pediatric Department of Services Hospital, Lahore for one year duration from July 2017 to July 2018.

Methods: A total of 150 cases that met the inclusion criteria were randomly selected. Proximal bowel biopsy and Immunological assay were done in all cases. The results were analyzed and explained in the proforma.

Results: The main complaints were lack of growth (81.07%) and diarrhea (78.93%). The main signs were short stature (88%) and anemia (72%). The typical biopsy findings were observed in all subjects. Most of the proven biopsy patients responded to a gluten-free diet (79%) and showed a significant correction in laboratory and clinical parameters.

Conclusion: The growth parameters and diarrhea improved significantly after treatment with a gradual reduction in anti tissue transglutaminase and serum antigliadin. Patients who did not fit adequately were mostly adolescence.

Key words: development, celiac disease, gluten.

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Please cite this article in press Rida Saghir et al., *Various Modes of Cleiac Disease Presentation in Children of 3-15 Years of Age.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Celiac disease is a condition in which the small intestine mucosa is damaged due to its sensitivity permanent to the gliadin fraction in the diet. Celiac disease associated enteropathy affects the proximal small intestine predominantly. In the diet, gluten presence is detrimental to the self-sustaining mucosa, while the destruction of gluten provides complete healing of the mucosa. The disease is determined genetically by HLA DR, DQ3, DR3, DQ2 confluency and limited reaction initiated by T cells in the intestinal epithelium. The celiac disease risk factors include type I diabetes mellitus, dermatitis herpetiformis, selective IgA deficiency, autoimmune thyroid disease, Down's syndrome, connective tissue disease, lymphocytic or collagenous colitis, neuromuscular or neurological disorders, and celiac disease family history. Celiac disease has variable modes and reference age. The average age is between three to five years, the typical disease is between 7 and 19 months and atypical in between 5 and 6 years. Classically, children have lack of growth, chronic diarrhea, anorexia, abdominal distension and muscle mass loss. Feces are pale, loose, bulky and extremely aggressive characteristics due to insufficient absorption of fat. Severe hypoproteinemia is observed in small number of infants and edema may be in the form of a celiac crisis.

RESULTS:

The results in detail are given in tables 1, 2 & 3

Table 1: Presenting complaints (n=150)

Complaints	n=	%age
Diarrhea	114	79.3
Vomiting	86	57.3
Failure to thrive	121	80.7
Bulky + Foul smelling stools	75	50.0
Abdominal pain	29	19.3
Anorexia	72	48.0

Immunological assays (n=150) results are given in Table 2.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This Observational descriptive study was held in the Pediatric Department of Services Hospital, Lahore for one year duration from July 2017 to July 2018. 150 patients were selected for the analysis. In Celiac disease, anti-tissue transglutaminase antibodies and anti-gliadin antibodies were confirmed in all cases with suspected clinical celiac disease between 2 and 15 years of age. Dysentery, persistent diarrhea, intestinal surgery, developmental delay, abdominal tuberculosis and weaning were not included in the study. Detailed systemic examination and General physical examination were performed and the findings were recorded. Research conducted to support the diagnosis; peripheral smear, complete blood count, stool microscopy, erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), culture sensitivity and routine examination, albumin, total serum proteins and electrolytes. Other diagnostic methods included serum antigliadin (IgG, IgA) qualitative analysis and serum tissue transglutaminase (IgG and IgA) by distal duodenal biopsy. Submucosal / total villous atrophy and submucosal lymphocyte proliferation and histopathological findings were taken as the gold standard diagnostic test. All results were documented in a specially designed format.

Table 2: Results of immunological assays (n=150)

Immunological Assay	No. of Patients with raised titer	%age
Serum anti gliadin IgA	123	82.0
IgG	113	75.3
Serum tissue transglutaminase IgA & IgG	146	97.3

Before and after treatment the effects of parameters are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Effects of parameters before and after treatment

Parameters	Before treatment (n=150)	After treatment (n=150)
Diarrhea	114 (79.3%)	99 (66%)
Growth parameters	114 (79.3%)	92 (61.3%)
Titre of anti-gliadin antibodies (IgA)	123 (82%)	110 (73.3%)
Antibodies IgG	114 (79.3%)	91 (60.7%)
Serum tissue transglutaminase IgA	148 (98.7%)	128 (85.3%)

DISCUSSION:

Celiac disease can occur in children under age of two years. Many malabsorption syndromes occur in mostly the same manner. Celiac disease can occur at any stage, after 40 years or early childhood with a peak. There are typical and atypical models of disease presentation. In the clinical presentation, most patients presented a combination of symptoms. The main symptoms in the 2 to 5-year age group, the main symptoms were between 6 to 11 years period, the main symptoms were malodorous or bulky stools, abdominal pain and anorexia, diarrhea, vomiting and developmental delay. Other studies on the presentation of celiac disease, syndrome, "classical" gastrointestinal malabsorption have been characterized by moderate symptoms such as gastrointestinal, bloating, abdominal pain, indigestion or other symptoms). Weaning is believed to be largely related to the symptoms development. For the development of celiac disease, the risk factor mainly is early weaning mainly in susceptible to genetic

affected patients. In this analysis, when most children are 5-6 months old, they usually have a history of weaning with rice and wheat based foods. Thirteen patients who were weaned six months later developed celiac disease after time in any part of life. Clemente et al. (2003), it was observed that the direct effects of gliadin on enterocytes could also increase intestinal permeability and lead to malabsorption. We note that these tests are useful for detecting the disease and that all patients have increased serum gliadin response (IgG and IgA) to verify tissue transglutaminase (IgG and IgA) in confirmatory studies of gluten disease. Free diet (90% and 98% sensitivity and 96% and 94% specificity respectively). Measurement of tissue transglutaminase antibody levels has a clear advantage over testing antibodies faster, easier and quantitatively, ie anti-endomiales. Some uses have been shown to have low sensitivity as low as 76%, but the two trials have exceeded the use of antibodies against gliadin. Systemic examination was normal in

most patients. A 17-year-old girl presented with symptoms at the age of three years with bowed legs, short stature, anemia, and hypoalbuminemia, and then celiac disease. Laboratory tests supporting the diagnosis were complete blood counts showing anemia of 71%. Some require constant training by patients and parents by doctors and dieticians. Now, there are cheaper immunoassays that have good diagnostic value, which is useful for monitoring treatment response. Superior superior GI endoscopy and for diagnosis biopsy remain the gold standard. All celiac disease patients should have a lifelong gluten-free diet, leading to the decrease in complications and also to the emergence of primary disease.

CONCLUSION:

Growth parameters and Diarrhea was significantly improved by the gradual reduction of serum titers of anti-tissue transglutaminase and antigliadin after treatment. Patients who did not fit adequately were mostly adolescence.

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